

Perception of Teachers and Students on Application of Artificial Intelligence in the Teaching and Learning of Mathematics in Wukari Metropolis, Taraba State, Nigeria.

FEKUMO Bolouembeledo, Ph.D¹

¹Department of Science Education,
Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.
fekumob@fuotuoke.edu.ng

&

HONMANE Onoge, Ph.D²

²Department of Science Education,
Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria.
honmane.onoge@fuwukari.edu.ng

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Abstract

This study investigated perception of teachers and students on the application of artificial intelligence in the teaching and learning of Mathematics. The research design was descriptive survey. The population of the study was 1230, which consists of mathematics teachers and Secondary School Two (SS2) students from all government owned secondary schools in Wukari Metropolis, Taraba State, Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling technique was used. Purposive sampling technique was used to select all the 20 mathematics teachers because their population is small, Whereas, 150 students were sampled from two schools out of 9 government owned senior secondary schools using a simple random sample technique. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire which was validated by measurement and evaluation experts. The instrument has a reliability index of 0.81, established using Cronbach alpha. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while chi-square was used to test the hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of this study among others showed that secondary school students are familiar with the use of AI in class during mathematics lesson which made some of them more receptive to its usage in secondary school and would like incorporating more AI based tools and software in teaching mathematics. Furthermore, mathematics teachers are familiar with the concept of artificial intelligence (AI). Also, using AI as an instructional strategy in mathematics class enhances students overall learning experience. Recommendations made among others, is that Interactive Software such as artificial intelligence should be incorporated among teaching strategies for teaching mathematical concepts.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Perception, Secondary School Students, Mathematics Teachers.

Introduction

Any country's ability to flourish depends on how well its students are taught mathematics, which lays the groundwork for future technological advancements. Mathematics is the gateway to science, and science serves as the foundation for technological advancement (Abakpa, Anyor, & Olaifa, 2017). Further acknowledgment was given to the value of mathematics in the contemporary culture of science and technology, with the assertion that without mathematics, science cannot exist, and without science, modern technology cannot exist, nor can modern society (Imoko & Isa,

2015). Furthermore, Zakariyya (2014) articulated mathematics as the primary tool for comprehending and investigating the worlds of science, technology, economics, society, and information. Since mathematics is the foundation for every nation's growth in science, industry, and technology, it is a topic of great importance. According to Iji, Honmane, and Omenka (2016), it is linked to greater academic and professional prospects.

Mathematics has seen a torrent of continual high failure despite the importance placed on it as a critical subject in attaining any nation's aspirations in science and technology (Ajinuhi & Honmane, 2024). This could be because there aren't any cutting-edge teaching strategies available to help teachers handle the difficulties of teaching the subject, particularly in the information age. Despite these obstacles, there are a number of ways to overcome the problems with Nigerian mathematical education. Using artificial intelligence (AI) technologies is one such opportunity. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the ability of a digital computer, computer-controlled machine or robot to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings like humans. (Mellor, 2022). Artificial intelligence (AI) is the replication of human intelligence by software-coded heuristics, according to Frankenfield (2023). The scientific field of artificial intelligence is concerned with creating and researching computers that are intended to enhance human intelligence. According to Alagbe et al. (2021), artificial intelligence (AI) is the capacity of a computer or machine to replicate the mental processes of a human, including learning from examples and experiences, object recognition, language understanding and response, decision-making, problem-solving, and combining these and other capabilities to perform tasks that a human might carry out, like checking into a hotel or operating a vehicle. Artificial Intelligence has the potential to enhance teacher preparation and growth, elevate the caliber of education, and track students' advancement. AI has the power to improve teacher preparation and professional development, which could revolutionize mathematics teaching in Nigeria. AI-powered online courses and resources can assist educators advance their pedagogical and subject-matter expertise. AI can also be utilized to design customized learning programs for educators, taking into account their unique requirements and areas for development. By doing this, you can make sure that educators get the assistance they require to succeed in the classroom (Ezenwobodo, 2024). AI can also be used to evaluate and track teachers' performance, offering recommendations and comments for development. AI has the potential to improve the quality of education by enabling teachers to tailor their lessons to each student's unique requirements and learning preferences (Moss, 2021). This feedback can be utilized to inspire and engage students, increasing learning effectiveness and enjoyment, as well as to assist them discover and solve their areas of weakness, enhancing their grasp of mathematics. One of the most effective ways to measure instructional practices is to use student and instructor ratings and feedback to assess the teaching approach (Anyagh, Honmane & Abah, 2018). Researchers in mathematics education have lately started to use instruments that are commonly used in scientific education to examine students' opinions of their classroom learning settings (Yang, 2013). Studies that have looked into how teachers and students see the teaching methodology are, nevertheless, scarce. Furthermore, there are few studies assessing how teachers and students perceive instructional approaches in the Nigerian educational context.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine:

1. How mathematics teachers perceived the potential benefits and challenges of incorporating AI as instructional strategy in secondary schools.

2. The mathematics teachers familiarity with AI technologies, and how does this familiarity influence their views and its uses as mathematics instruction in secondary schools.
3. The attitudes and perceptions of students regarding the use of AI as a teaching and learning tool in their mathematics class in secondary schools.
4. The level of exposure and experience with AI technologies among students impact their mathematics understanding in secondary schools.

Research Questions

1. How do mathematics teachers perceive the potential benefits and challenges of incorporating AI as instructional strategy in secondary schools?
2. To what extent are mathematics teachers familiar with AI technologies, and how does this familiarity influence their views and its uses as mathematics instruction in secondary schools?
3. What are the attitude and perceptions of students regarding the use of AI as a teaching and learning tool in their mathematics class in secondary schools?
4. How does the level of exposure and experience with AI technologies among students impact their mathematics understanding in secondary schools?

Research Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference in the attitudes and perceptions of mathematics teachers towards the use of AI in the teaching of mathematics in secondary schools.
2. There is no significant difference in the attitudes and perceptions of students regarding the use of AI as a teaching and learning tool in their mathematics class in secondary schools.

Significance of the Study

The unusual approach taken by this study examined how teachers and secondary school students felt about artificial intelligence (AI) in the context of math instruction. There are various reasons why this study is significant. First of all, because they are the only real witnesses to what takes place in the classroom, the study looks at how students and teachers perceive mathematical instructional methods. Besides that, the results may provide useful information to the educational administrators in providing new systems of assessing instructional practices. Additionally, by better understanding how educators and students view AI, more effective teaching methods may be developed, which may boost math proficiency among kids.

Methodology

This study used a cross-sectional survey design as its research methodology. Still, the study was carried out in Taraba State, Nigeria's Wukari Metropolis. 1230 Secondary School Two (SS 2) students from nine state-owned Secondary Schools including mathematics teachers in the study area made up the study's population. The method of multistage sampling was applied. Because there are only 20 math teachers, a purposive/convenient sampling technique was employed to choose all of them, and a simple random sample technique was utilized to choose 150 students from a population of 1210. Secondary school two (SS2) was also chosen using purposive/convenient sampling technique. This was mostly because they were accustomed to the classroom setting, having just completed their second year of secondary school. Furthermore, they have studied mathematics in school for a sufficient amount of time to allow evaluation of their attitudes and views A questionnaire using a four-point Likert-type scale for each topic (Strongly

Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree) served as the data gathering tool. Measurement and assessment specialists validated it. Cronbach alpha was used to determine the dependability index of the instrument, which stands at 0.81. Scores are allocated according to a scale as follows: 1, 2, 3, 4 for responses SA, A, D, and SD for things classified as negative (-), and 4, 3, 2, 1 for responses SA, A, D, and SD for items classified as positive (+). That means that 2.5 is the average (mean). this was calculated by adding the point scale (4+3+2+1=10) and dividing the total by 4, or 10/4. A mean score of 2.50 or higher was deemed acceptable, whereas a mean score of 2.50 or lower was deemed unacceptable (accepted mean indicates positive attitude and perception, rejected mean indicates negative attitude and perception). The study questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation, and the hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance using the Chi-square method.

Results

Presentation of results are done in accordance with the research questions asked and hypotheses formulated.

Research Question 1

How do mathematics teachers perceive the potential benefits and challenges of incorporating AI as instructional strategy in secondary schools? Answer to this research question is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings of Attitudes and Perceptions of Mathematics Teachers Potential Benefits and Challenges of Incorporating AI as Instructional Strategy in Secondary Schools.

S/N	Description	Mean	S.D	Remark
1.	AI can aid individualize mathematics teaching intended for students.	3.05	0.97	Accepted
2.	Problem-solving skills can be improved via the utilization of AI in mathematics instruction	2.65	1.06	Accepted
3.	Students engagement regarding mathematics studies could be enhanced by AI aided instruction	2.90	1.10	Accepted
4	I do not like AI use in the teaching and learning of mathematics because reduces interaction between the teacher and students.	2.35	1.05	Rejected
5.	I love AI because it is enabled to assess students' progress without any form of bias	2.66	0.96	Accepted
	Grand Mean.	2.72	1.03	Accepted

From the table 1 above, the grand mean of 2.72 is above the criterion mean of 2.50, it reveals that mathematics teachers are bent to believe that AI is capable of enhancing teaching and learning of secondary schools mathematics.

Research Question 2

To what extent are mathematics teachers familiar with AI technologies, and how does this familiarity influence their views and its uses as mathematics instruction in secondary schools? Answer to this research question is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings of Mathematics Teachers Familiarity With AI Technologies, and How Does This Familiarity Influence Their Views and its Uses as Mathematics Instruction In Secondary Schools.

S/N	Description	Mean	S.D	Remark
1.	The idea of artificial intelligence (AI) is well-known among mathematics teachers.	2.80	0.95	Accepted
2.	I have incorporated AI tools into my math instruction.	2.30	0.96	Rejected
3.	I think my knowledge of AI has a favorable impact on how I see its application in mathematics classrooms.	3.05	0.88	Accepted
4.	Relying upon AI as a medium of instruction might aid in the loss of jobs by mathematics teachers.	3.15	0.93	Accepted
5.	Teachers teaching mathematics are excited about integrating AI to improve the teaching of mathematics.	2.30	1.12	Rejected
	Grand Mean.	2.72	1.03	Accepted

Table 2 shows a 2.72 grand mean. This is above 2.50 criterion mean, implying that mathematics teachers are of the view that their experience in AI is reason behind their positive perspective on its usage.

Research Question 3

What are the attitudes and perceptions of students regarding the use of AI as a teaching and learning tool in their mathematics class in secondary schools? Answer to this research question is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings of Attitudes and Perceptions of Students Regarding the Use of AI as a Teaching and Learning Tool in their Mathematics Class in Secondary Schools.

S/N	Description	Mean	S.D	Remark
1.	AI is a useful and necessary tool for studying mathematics.	3.04	0.97	Accepted
2.	More AI-based resources and technologies in math instruction is something I would want to see my mathematics teacher use.	3.13	0.94	Accepted
3.	The use of AI in teaching mathematics contributes to the overall students' learning experience.	2.68	0.95	Accepted
4.	AI in mathematics class prepares students for future technological advancements.	2.66	0.99	Accepted
	Grand Mean.	2.88	0.98	Accepted

From the table 3 above, the grand mean of 2.88, in this case, is above the criterion mean of 2.50, a clear indication that the students have positive attitude and perception to the use of AI as an essential tool and effective for mathematics learning.

Research Question 4

How does the level of exposure and experience with AI technologies among students impact their mathematics understanding in secondary schools? Answer to this research question is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings of the Level of Exposure and Experience with AI Technologies among Students Impact their Mathematics Understanding in Secondary Schools.

S/N	Description	Mean	S.D	Remark
1.	I have knowledge of AI tools for mathematics instructions	2.10	1.03	Rejected
2.	My knowledge of AI for mathematics instructions actually contributed in my perception of it being used in mathematics teaching and learning in schools.	2.27	1.02	Rejected
3.	Students previously exposed to AI will most likely do better in mathematics.	2.93	0.98	Accepted
4.	I'm willing to explore innovative AI tools for mathematics learning.	3.18	0.95	Accepted
5.	My exposure to AI has increased my openness to its applications in secondary schools.	2.42	1.01	Rejected
	Grand Mean.	2.58	1.00	Accepted

Table 4 shows that the grand mean of 2.58 is above the criterion mean of 2.50. This by implication means majority of the students who responded to the questionnaire are of the opinion that students who AI compliance are most likely to excel in their mathematics.

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the attitudes and perceptions of mathematics teachers towards the use of AI in the teaching of mathematics in secondary schools. The result of this hypothesis is presented in Table 5.

TABLE 5: Chi-Square Result of the Attitudes and Perceptions of Mathematics Teachers Towards the use of AI in the Teaching of Mathematics in Secondary Schools.

Number of Teachers	DF	X ² Cal.	X ² Crit.	Level of Sign.	Decision
20	9	4.23	15.32	0.05	Accepted

According to the data in Table 5, the crucial chi-square value stands at 15.32, which is above the calculated value of 4.23. Thus, the null hypothesis was upheld. Hence, there is no significant difference in the attitudes and perceptions of mathematics teachers towards the use of AI in the teaching of mathematics in secondary schools.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the attitudes and perceptions of students regarding the use of AI as a teaching and learning tool in their mathematics class in secondary schools. The result of this hypothesis is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Chi-Square Result of the Attitudes and Perceptions of Students Regarding the use of AI as a Teaching and Learning Tool in their Mathematics Class in Secondary Schools.

Number of Students	DF	X ² Cal.	X ² Crit.	Level of Sign.	Decision
150	12	48.66	20.02	0.05	Rejected

According to the data in Table 6, the crucial chi-square value stands at 20.024, falling below the calculated value of 48.66. Therefore the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there is a significant difference in the attitudes and perceptions of students regarding the use of AI as a teaching and learning tool in their mathematics class in secondary schools.

Summary of Findings

The key conclusions drawn were derived from the data provided in this study:

1. There is no significant difference in the attitudes and perceptions of mathematics teachers towards the use of AI in the teaching of mathematics in secondary schools.
2. There is a significant difference in the attitudes and perceptions of students regarding the use of AI as a teaching and learning tool in their mathematics class in secondary schools.

Discussion of Findings

The result showed that the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in mathematics classrooms has been met with enthusiasm by mathematics teachers and has resulted in notable improvements in secondary school mathematics instruction. This outcome is consistent with a study by Ezenwobodo (2024), which discovered that there is no significant difference in the perceptions of mathematics educators and students regarding the employment of AI in the classroom. This is in agreement with the outcome of this study. Furthermore, many secondary school students are familiar with the use of application of AI in class during mathematics lesson which made some of them more receptive to its uses in secondary school and would like incorporating more AI based tools and software in teaching mathematics. This finding is in agreement with the research result of Mark (2023) who found a significant difference in the potential of artificial Intelligence as a teaching and learning tool in Nigerian schools, which is the same with the outcome of this study.

Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate how barely artificial intelligence (AI) is utilized in secondary school mathematics instruction. The study also showed that integrating AI tools and technology into secondary school mathematics instruction will help students become more adept at solving problems and will boost the subject's overall teaching and learning. According to the survey, teachers are also quite worried that AI would take the position of mathematics teachers and that it might make students less interested in mathematics classes.

Recommendations

The conclusions drawn from this study led to the formulation of the following suggestions:

1. Utilizing interactive software like artificial intelligence should be integrated into teaching methods for imparting mathematical concepts.
2. School owners ought to make an effort to buy artificial intelligence software for their students' use in the classroom.

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